

Stress-relieved Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si high-entropy alloys: a path for enhancing the magnetocaloric response

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In this study, we further subject the recently found Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si high-entropy alloys (HEAs) exhibiting first-order thermomagnetic phase transition to designed heat treatments. The results reveal that the standard heat treatments transform the as-cast dual-phase microstructure into a single phase without influencing the magnetocaloric response or average composition. A crucial observation is the substantial enhancement in magnetocaloric effects and transition temperatures achieved through a low-temperature heat treatment at 673 K, while maintaining the microstructures and compositions of the alloys. The optimized annealed Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si HEA samples show exceptional magnetocaloric effects, surpassing previous studies and positioning them as strong contenders against established conventional high-performing magnetocaloric materials. The changes in magnetic anisotropy distribution are indicative of the stress relaxation induced by low-temperature annealing. This work shows that stress relaxation can have a significant effect on the optimization of magnetocaloric response, even more important than achieving a single phase by annealing at higher temperatures.

Keywords: magnetocaloric effect; high-entropy alloys; first-order magnetostructural phase transition; stress relaxation; magnetic anisotropy

Magnetocaloric high-entropy alloys (HEAs) have recently garnered widespread attention and recognition as a compelling and pivotal group of magnetocaloric materials [1, 2]. These unique alloys are designed with a specific focus on compositions consisting of four or more principal elements, resulting in a high configurational entropy of mixing (ΔS_{mix}) and the remarkable ability to form solid solutions. While the initial emphasis of HEAs revolved around equiatomic compositions to maximize the configurational entropy of mixing, significant strides have been made in the development of non-equiatomic and multiphase HEAs, showcasing exceptional mechanical properties [3, 4] (where the threshold for ΔS_{mix} for quinary HEA is considered to be at least 1.5 times the ideal gas constant, R [5, 6]). This has not only expanded the scope of alloying possibilities but has also facilitated the tailored design of properties to meet specific requirements. While HEA research has predominantly centered on exploring their mechanical properties, especially in terms of strengthening methodologies and achieving high strength in extreme temperature conditions, there have been limited reports on their functional potential [7-10], such as their magnetic, magnetocaloric, and catalytic properties. Furthermore, their initial magnetocaloric reports indicate values that are not on par with high-performance conventional magnetocaloric materials. However, a recent targeted search approach has unveiled substantial untapped potential within the extensive compositional space of HEAs [11, 12]. Notably, the $(\text{FeMnNi})_{66.7}(\text{GeSi})_{33.3}$ HEA system has demonstrated a remarkable magnetocaloric effect stemming from the first-order thermomagnetic phase transition (FOMT) linked to the orthorhombic \leftrightarrow hexagonal phase transformation. This transformation has resulted in a magnetocaloric effect (MCE) as large as $13 \text{ J kg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ under a magnetic field change of 2.5 T, igniting a surge in research efforts focusing on related compositions. Furthermore, it has been coined as the third-generation magnetocaloric HEAs and considered as one of the cutting-edge functional high-entropy

materials from recent perspectives paper on HEAs [13]. It has further inspired the design of magnetic HEAs, propelling the relevant compositional system (quasi-equiatomic $\text{Cr}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x}\text{MnCoNiGeSi}$, MnNiSiFeCoGe HEAs) for barocaloric or magnetocaloric applications [14-17]. Highly random distributions of each element observed in both FeMnCoNiGeSi and CrMnCoNiGeSi HEAs, within both hexagonal and orthorhombic lattices, without local segregations, support their classification as high entropy solid solutions [15]. Another recent study, building upon the aforementioned breakthrough, endeavored to investigate crystalline rare-earth-containing HEAs featuring unconventional crystal structures, specifically the orthorhombic structure observed in GdErHoCoM ($M = \text{Cr}$ or Mn), departing from the more commonly documented hexagonal close-packed (HCP), face-centered cubic (FCC), and body-centered cubic (BCC) structures [18]. Furthermore, these advancements have broadened the compositional diversity of HEAs for potential applications in solid-state refrigeration and have facilitated the design of functional HEAs.

Researchers typically study the as-cast states of $\text{Mn/Fe-Ni/Co-Ge/Si/Al}$, or their post-annealed states, but this usually involves subjecting the as-cast ingots to annealing at temperatures of 800 °C and above [19-25]. It is important to note that these reports [19-22] systematically compared the influence of annealing profiles on the behavior of the samples. Overall, they found that the phase transition temperatures show notable sensitivity to the heat-treatment conditions, specifically in the use of anneal-quenched or cyclic-aged treatments at annealing temperatures of 773 K and above [22]. In comparing the behavior of as-cast and aged-treated MnCoGe at temperatures of 773 K and higher, it is found that annealing at elevated temperatures results in a reduction of structural transformation temperatures. Notably, the application of high-temperature anneal-

quenching and low-temperature cyclical aging in the Mn-Co-Ge alloy system results in the generation of multiple phase states and an increase in phase transformation temperatures with rising anneal-quenching temperatures, varying from 973 to 1273 K [19].

In this work, we applied thermal treatments to our groundbreaking FOMT- FeMnNiGeSi HEAs [11, 12] aimed to achieve further enhancement in their MCE. We hypothesized that having similar compositions to conventional ternary systems, they would also be responsive to the design of heat treatments. We discovered no alteration to prior microstructures and compositions occurred when heat-treated $\text{Fe}_{0.23}\text{Mn}_{0.24}\text{Ni}_{0.23}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})_{0.30}$ (where $x = 0.50$ and 0.45) HEAs at low temperatures of 673 K. Yet, these treatments yield a remarkable enhancement of the MCE and transition temperatures. Moreover, the transformation of the as-cast dual-phase microstructure into a single phase upon annealing at 1073 K (a typical annealing temperature reported in the literature) did not compromise the average composition or the magnetocaloric response. Our results clearly indicate that the creation of a single-phase structure does not inherently enhance the MCE. Notably, the optimized annealed Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si HEA samples can exhibit outstanding magnetocaloric effect, surpassing those of prior reports and other reported HEAs. These compelling results underscore the potential of HEAs to compete with established conventional magnetocaloric materials, such as $\text{La}(\text{Fe},\text{Si})_{13}$, Fe_2P , and $\text{Gd}_5\text{Si}_2\text{Ge}_2$.

As-cast alloys were produced by arc melting from raw constituent elements (of at least 99.9% purity) under an Ar-controlled atmosphere, with $\text{Fe}_{0.23}\text{Mn}_{0.24}\text{Ni}_{0.23}(\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x})_{0.30}$ (where $x = 0.50$ and 0.45) as the nominal compositions. The ingots underwent four remelts, each time being flipped, and were then annealed for four days and quenched in

water. We initially followed the conventional heat treatment methodology reported in the literature: annealed the samples at 1073 K. Additionally, we annealed the as-cast samples at 673 K. For the annealing experiments, the as-cast samples were enclosed in Ta film and sealed in Ar-filled quartz tubes. The studied samples are designated based on their nominal $\text{Ge}_x\text{Si}_{1-x}$ composition, as well as whether they were as-cast or annealed at specific temperatures. They are, namely, as-cast, 1073 K-annealed and 673 K-annealed. Based on the obtained results, we decided to also apply a subsequent thermal treatment at 673 K on the previously 1073 K-annealed samples, denoted as 1073+673 K-annealed.

Their microstructures and compositional analysis were characterized using the FEI Teneo scanning electron microscope, equipped with backscatter electron and energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) detectors. The thermomagnetic behaviors were investigated with a LakeShore 8607 vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) with magnetic fields up to 1.5 T. The 673-annealed samples were further measured up to 2.5 T with the VSM option of a Quantum Design PPMS. The isothermal entropy change, ΔS_{iso} , was determined from isothermal magnetization (M) vs. magnetic field (H) measurement data, in which the measurements were carried out following the discontinuous measurement protocols [26] designed to erase the prior memory of the sample between each isothermal measurement. The implementation of this protocol ensures the prevention of spurious results irrespective of the order of the thermomagnetic phase transition [26, 27]:

$$\Delta S_{iso} = \mu_0 \int_0^H \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial T} \right)_{H'} dH'. \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. As-cast samples versus annealing them at 1073 K: (a) Backscattered electron micrographs and the corresponding EDX analysis reveal dual-phase microstructures (with minority Si-depleted regions) in the as-cast samples change to homogenous single-phase microstructures upon annealing at 1073 K. Their corresponding **(b)** isofield $M(T)$ and **(c)** isothermal entropy change curves (measured up to 1.5 T in cooling).

Upon annealing the as-cast $\text{Ge}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5}$ and $\text{Ge}_{0.45}\text{Si}_{0.55}$ samples at 1073 K, the dual-phase microstructures undergo homogenization, resulting in a single-phase formation as depicted in **Figure 1 (a)**. The dual-phase microstructure observed in the as-cast states is consistent with prior reports [11, 12]. The lighter contrast region corresponds to the nominal composition, accompanied by Ge-depleted darker contrast regions. Details on the phase compositions are summarized in **Table 1**, presenting that the single-phase microstructure attained upon annealing at 1073 K yields a phase composition in good agreement with the nominal. Despite homogenizing into a single phase, no discernible changes are found in their overall thermomagnetic and isothermal entropy change (ΔS_{iso}) curves, as shown in **Figure 1 (b)** and **(c)**. The as-cast $\text{Ge}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5}$ and $\text{Ge}_{0.45}\text{Si}_{0.55}$ samples for low fields demonstrate an increase in magnetization with increasing temperature

caused by the stronger magnetic anisotropy of the orthorhombic phase followed by ferromagnetic to paramagnetic (FM–PM) transition of the hexagonal phase, resulting in the manifestation of inverse and conventional MCE for low fields. For high fields, the influence of the magnetic anisotropy is reduced, resulting in a decrease of magnetization with increasing temperature followed by the Curie transition of the hexagonal phase, both being conventional MCE. This is unchanged for 1073 K-annealed $\text{Ge}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5}$ samples. However, upon a closer examination of the 1073 K-annealed $\text{Ge}_{0.45}\text{Si}_{0.55}$ samples, the anisotropy variation is reduced due to their slightly higher transition temperature which suppresses anisotropy contribution and results in conventional MCE for both low and high magnetic fields.

Table 1. Measured compositions of the studied HEA series with their empirical parameters.

Nominal Composition	Sample ID	Measured Composition	δ (%) ^a	$ \Delta S_{mix} $ ($\text{J mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) ^b	
$\text{Fe}_{0.23}\text{Mn}_{0.24}\text{Ni}_{0.23}$ ($\text{Ge}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5}$) _{0.30}	Ge_{0.5}Si_{0.5} – as-cast	Darker-contrast regions	$\text{Fe}_{24.1}\text{Mn}_{22.5}\text{Ni}_{21.3}$ $\text{Ge}_{12.5}\text{Si}_{19.6}$	3.1	1.59 R
		Lighter-contrast regions	$\text{Fe}_{22.1}\text{Mn}_{24.9}\text{Ni}_{21.7}$ $\text{Ge}_{16.3}\text{Si}_{15.0}$	3.3	1.59 R
	Ge_{0.5}Si_{0.5} – 1073 K	1-phase	$\text{Fe}_{23.5}\text{Mn}_{23.6}\text{Ni}_{21.7}$ $\text{Ge}_{15.0}\text{Si}_{16.2}$	3.2	1.59 R
	Ge_{0.5}Si_{0.5} – 673 K	Darker-contrast regions	$\text{Fe}_{25.8}\text{Mn}_{21.2}\text{Ni}_{21.1}$ $\text{Ge}_{11.9}\text{Si}_{20.0}$	3.1	1.58 R
		Lighter-contrast regions	$\text{Fe}_{19.4}\text{Mn}_{27.1}\text{Ni}_{22.3}$ $\text{Ge}_{19.3}\text{Si}_{11.9}$	3.5	1.58 R
	Ge_{0.5}Si_{0.5} – 1073+673 K	1-phase	$\text{Fe}_{23.1}\text{Mn}_{23.7}\text{Ni}_{21.8}$ $\text{Ge}_{15.1}\text{Si}_{16.3}$	3.3	1.59 R
$\text{Fe}_{0.23}\text{Mn}_{0.24}\text{Ni}_{0.23}$ ($\text{Ge}_{0.45}\text{Si}_{0.55}$) _{0.30}	Ge_{0.45}Si_{0.55} – as-cast	Darker-contrast regions	$\text{Fe}_{24.8}\text{Mn}_{22.4}\text{Ni}_{21.3}$ $\text{Ge}_{10.9}\text{Si}_{20.6}$	3.0	1.58 R
		Lighter-contrast regions	$\text{Fe}_{18.6}\text{Mn}_{28.3}\text{Ni}_{22.1}$ $\text{Ge}_{18.4}\text{Si}_{12.6}$	3.4	1.58 R
	Ge_{0.45}Si_{0.55} – 1073 K	1-phase	$\text{Fe}_{22.9}\text{Mn}_{24.0}\text{Ni}_{21.4}$ $\text{Ge}_{13.6}\text{Si}_{18.0}$	3.2	1.59 R
	Ge_{0.45}Si_{0.55} – 673 K	Darker-contrast regions	$\text{Fe}_{23.4}\text{Mn}_{23.4}\text{Ni}_{21.2}$ $\text{Ge}_{10.9}\text{Si}_{21.1}$	3.0	1.58 R
		Lighter-contrast regions	$\text{Fe}_{21.3}\text{Mn}_{25.7}\text{Ni}_{21.8}$ $\text{Ge}_{15.6}\text{Si}_{15.6}$	3.3	1.59 R
	Ge_{0.45}Si_{0.55} – 1073+673 K	1-phase	$\text{Fe}_{23.1}\text{Mn}_{23.9}\text{Ni}_{21.3}$ $\text{Ge}_{13.6}\text{Si}_{18.1}$	3.2	1.59 R

^a δ is the atomic size difference; constraints of δ for HEAs containing light elements are $\leq 4.5\%$.

^b ΔS_{mix} is the entropy of mixing; The requirement for HEAs: $1.5\text{ R} < \Delta S_{mix} \leq 1.61\text{ R}$ (for quinary alloy) where R is the gas constant. Calculations were based on refs. [28-30].

Figure 2. Samples annealed at 673 K: (a) Backscattered electron micrographs and the corresponding EDX analysis reveal dual-phase microstructures (with minority Si-depleted regions) upon annealing at 673 K, similar to the as-cast samples. Their corresponding (b) isofield $M(T)$ and (c) isothermal entropy change curves (measured up to 1.5 T in cooling) reveal FM-PM behavior for low and high magnetic fields, yielding MCE enhancement compared to as-cast counterparts.

In contrast, annealing the as-cast samples at 673 K results in the retainment of dual-phase microstructures (**Figure 2 (a)**) and brings upon a notable enhancement in their ΔS_{iso} values, alongside a shift towards higher temperatures (**Figure 2 (b)** and (c)). The initial distinction of 673-annealed samples versus as-cast counterparts is apparent in $M(T)$ results: the former demonstrates only FM-PM transitions for both 0.05 and 1 T. The ΔS_{iso} results (1.5 T) of 673 K-annealed samples demonstrate a 1.2–1.9-fold enhancement in their maximum values and a 40 – 46 K rise in their corresponding peak temperatures. These results indicate that 673 K-annealed samples exhibit unique outcomes compared to those treated with conventional high-temperature annealing, typically 1073 K or above, as commonly reported in the literature [20, 23-25, 31]. This suggests that stress relaxation

achieved by annealing at lower temperatures improves performance, while achieving homogenized microstructures minimally impacts the magnetocaloric response in Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si HEA.

Figure 3. 1073 K-annealed samples further annealed at 673 K: (a) Backscattered electron micrographs and the corresponding EDX analysis reveal that the single-phase microstructures are retained consistent with the 1073-annealed samples. Yet their corresponding (b) isofield $M(T)$ and (c) isothermal entropy change curves (measured up to 1.5 T in cooling) reveal FM-PM behavior for low and high magnetic fields, yielding MCE enhancement compared to as-cast counterparts.

To verify the aforementioned hypothesis about stress-relaxation resulting from low-temperature annealing, the samples previously annealed at 1073 K were subjected to further annealing at 673 K. No alteration to the achieved single-phase microstructures or significant compositional change is observed as shown in **Figure 3 (a)** and **Table 1** (as compared to 1073 K-annealed counterparts). However, the thermomagnetic behavior of the samples annealed at 1073 K differ from those with the combined annealing at 1073 K followed by 673 K (see **Figure 3 (b)**). The 1073 K-annealed samples show two types of

behavior at low and high magnetic fields as mentioned above. Further annealing at 673 K (1073+673 K annealing) not only leads to an increase in the transition temperatures, but also results in only a single FM–PM transition throughout without the contribution of the magnetocrystalline anisotropy at low fields. These two features are in line with the results of the 673 K-annealed sample. **Figure 3 (c)** demonstrates that the ΔS_{iso} values undergo an enhancement of up to 1.8 times, accompanied by an increase in their corresponding peak temperatures, within the range of 31 – 34 K. In related Cr-Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si HEAs reported in the literature, pressure induces a decrease in the transition temperatures [15]. In our work, upon the low temperature annealing, the transition temperatures shift towards higher values even in the absence of compositional changes. This finding supports the proposition that the effect is associated with stress relaxation.

Figure 4. (a) The influence of annealing treatment on the absolute peak values of ΔS_{iso} (1.5 T). The homogenization route of the as-cast samples is further grey-shaded and indicated by dashed arrows. The pinkish region and routes indicated by solid arrows represent the stress relaxation treatment. (b) Distribution of magnetic anisotropy ($P(H_K)$) for $Ge_{0.5}Si_{0.5}$.

The influence of annealing profiles on the MCE of the investigated Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si HEA series (measured up to 1.5 T) is succinctly presented in **Figure 4 (a)**. Annealing the samples at 1073 K clearly led to a single-phase microstructure, indicating a successful homogenization treatment (shown by the grey-shaded region and dashed arrows). Nonetheless, this treatment did not demonstrate significant effects on the MCE. On the contrary, annealing at 673 K enhances the MCE without altering the previous microstructures (indicated by the solid arrows) maintaining dual-phase if the annealing starts from as-cast state, or single-phase if from 1073 K-annealed samples. This enhancement also hints at the stress relaxation achieved (highlighted as pinkish-shaded region) during low-temperature annealing, even leading to a decrease in thermal hysteresis: the 673 K-annealed samples experience reductions from 26 \rightarrow 12 K and 12 \rightarrow 4 K (compared to as-cast states) for $\text{Ge}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5}$ and $\text{Ge}_{0.45}\text{Si}_{0.55}$, respectively. On the other hand, annealing at 1073 K resulted in samples retaining similar hysteresis values to the as-cast states.

Stress relaxation could be, in principle, detected by microdiffraction experiments by changing the orientation of the sample. However, the strong texture of the sample prevents this analysis, as diffraction peaks disappear from the area detector upon changes in orientation. It is also important to note that these samples can undergo modification through grinding or polishing, which can impact their microstructures as demonstrated in alloys undergoing magnetostructural transformations [32-35]. These circumstances prevent us from determining stress relaxation from X-ray diffraction experiments. Alternatively, we have analysed the evolution of magnetic anisotropy distribution upon annealing, in an analogous way to the analysis made to study the relaxation and crystallization of amorphous alloys [36]. The main virtue of this method is that it does not require sample preparation that might affect microstructure or stress due to

processing. As indicated above, low-temperature annealing does not alter the composition or crystal structure of the samples, i.e. magnetocrystalline anisotropy remains unchanged. On the other hand, the specimens of the alloys were selected exhibiting similar sample shapes, thereby eliminating differences in the shape contribution to anisotropy [37]. Hence, changes in the anisotropy distribution implies changes in magnetoelastic anisotropy. The distribution of magnetic anisotropy was determined from magnetization curves in the orthorhombic phase ($P(H_K) = -H \frac{\partial^2 m}{\partial H^2}$ where H_K is the anisotropy field and m the normalized magnetization [36, 38, 39]). The results of $\text{Ge}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5}$ samples depicted in **Figure 4 (b)** (refer to supplementary material for $\text{Ge}_{0.45}\text{Si}_{0.55}$) reveal that annealing at 673 K notably shifts the distribution to lower field values, as well as reduces its width. For a clearer comparison, the top panel shows as-cast vs. 673 K-annealed, and the bottom panel the 1073 K-annealed vs. 1073+673 K-annealed samples. These observations indicate a decrease in magnetoelastic anisotropy and therefore stress relaxation during low-temperature annealing.

Figure 5. 673 K-annealed samples analysis: (a) Isothermal entropy change curves remeasured up to 2.5 T (arrows indicate increasing field) for (b) further comparison with reported magnetocaloric HEAs and other relevant conventional magnetocaloric materials (in terms of the absolute peak values of ΔS_{iso} and corresponding peak temperatures for 2 T). Spheres represent HEAs while open symbols for conventional magnetocaloric materials. Literature data are taken from refs. [7, 8, 40-47].

A further thermomagnetic analysis was performed on the 673 K-annealed samples to examine their magnetocaloric responses at elevated magnetic fields. Their results show conventional MCE behavior as depicted in **Figure 5 (a)**, albeit with larger peak values (compared to **Figure 3 (c)**) attributed to higher magnetic fields. **Figure 5 (b)** provides an overview of the current work versus the state-of-the-art magnetocaloric HEAs (spherical symbols) and conventional magnetocaloric materials (open symbols). This performance comparison is based on their $|\Delta S_{\text{iso}}^{\text{peak}}|$ values for 2 T (typical magnetic field assumed for permanent magnets in magnetocaloric devices) and corresponding peak temperatures. We include the preceding results of the as-cast Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si HEAs (detailed in ref. [11, 12]), as they effectively filled the pre-existing gap between magnetocaloric HEA and conventional magnetocaloric materials, influencing the emergence of non-equiatomic magnetocaloric HEA. It has been observed that the optimally annealed HEA samples of

this work have unequivocally outperformed all other magnetocaloric HEAs, showcasing performance levels that can rival renowned conventional materials, such as $\text{La}(\text{Fe},\text{Si})_{13}$, Fe_2P , and $\text{Gd}_5\text{Si}_2\text{Ge}_2$.

In summary, the results obtained from the study unequivocally establish that annealing the Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si HEAs at lower temperatures, specifically at 673 K, significantly improves the magnetocaloric effect. This improvement is reflected in a remarkable up to 1.8-fold increase in isothermal entropy change and in higher transition temperatures. Importantly, these enhancements are achieved with a decrease in thermal hysteresis, without any alteration to the existing microstructure or compositions. Furthermore, combining homogenization with stress relaxation annealing also results in an improved magnetocaloric response. Notably, the optimized annealed Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si HEA samples demonstrate superior magnetocaloric effects compared to other reported HEAs, and they can even rival established conventional materials, such as $\text{La}(\text{Fe},\text{Si})_{13}$, Fe_2P , and $\text{Gd}_5\text{Si}_2\text{Ge}_2$.

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CRediT author statement

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Stress-relieved Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si high-entropy alloys: a path for enhancing the magnetocaloric response

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A discontinuous measurement protocol [1] to erase the previous history of the sample during the isothermal $M(H)$ measurements was conducted. The discontinuous protocol is implemented to prevent spurious results, regardless of the order of the thermomagnetic phase transition, which has been reported to impact the use of the Maxwell relation for calculating $\Delta S_{\text{isothermal}}$ [1,2]. Figure S1 shows the measured $M(H)$ curves of the studied samples.

Figure S1: $M(H)$ curves for the series of studied Fe-Mn-Ni-Ge-Si HEAs: as-cast versus the different post-annealing.

In addition, these samples exhibit a high degree of texture, significantly impacting their XRD characterization. The figure below demonstrates the level of texturization in the samples, exemplified by diffraction points instead of rings, as observed in the case of the as-cast $\text{Ge}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5}$ sample.

Figure S2: Highly textured characteristics observed from the diffraction points (instead of rings) during X-ray microdiffraction experiments for as-cast $\text{Ge}_{0.5}\text{Si}_{0.5}$ sample.

Distribution of magnetic anisotropy ($P(H_K)$) for $\text{Ge}_{0.45}\text{Si}_{0.55}$ showing the shift down to lower anisotropy field values as well as reduced width caused by the low-temperature annealing is depicted in Figure S3. When compared to the $\text{Ge}_{0.50}\text{Si}_{0.50}$ sample, this annealing-induced change in magnetoelastic anisotropy is smaller in the $\text{Ge}_{0.45}\text{Si}_{0.55}$ case, leading to a less significant modification of the magnitude of the magnetocaloric response.

Figure S3: Distribution of magnetic anisotropy ($P(H_K)$) for $\text{Ge}_{0.45}\text{Si}_{0.55}$.

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